

DOMESTIC VIOLENCE AND WAYS TO PREVENT IT

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Abstract. *Today, a new concept in human society is family the term violence has arrived. Domestic violence – own a global problem in terms of scale. In this article the origin of this term and this type of violence the causative factors and their prevention are discussed.*

Keywords: *family violence, society, islamic violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, economic violence.*

Today, one of the top priorities for our state and administration is to ensure a stable and healthy socio-spiritual environment, peace, harmony in society, and support for difficult families, particularly for the women and children who live in them. If the family is peaceful, the neighborhood, the nation, and the children raised there will be psychologically and intellectually healthy. If the rights and interests of women are protected, the conditions for giving birth to and raising psychologically and intellectually healthy children will be set.

It is no secret that the evil of violence still exists in society despite the fact that a number of legislative papers have been approved to defend the rights and interests of women and to eradicate violence. Violence against women is seen as a very severe issue when it comes to the violation of human rights in any community, whether it occurs in the home, at work, or on the streets.

In general, violence is the effect of one person on another. The main purpose of such influence is to harm another against his will. Psychology considers violence as a form of manifestation of mental and / or physical coercion against one of the interacting parties who is forced to do something against their will, desires, needs. In this case, a party can be understood as a person or a group of people. Psychology also considers violence to be any act of controlling the behavior of another person, imposing one's will and views on him, as well as controlling the thoughts and feelings of another person against his will and desire. In this case, the extortionist seeks to get the maximum benefit. Basically, domestic violence is the same thing, only it all happens in the same family.

Domestic abuse affects more women and children. About 14,000 women each year in Russia die as a result of domestic abuse, and 78% of Russian children endure some kind of maltreatment. Domestic abuse mostly takes the following four forms:

- Islamic violence;
- psychological violence;
- sexual violence;
- economic violence.

We will think about them carefully.

One of the most prevalent forms of violence is physical violence. Any physical impact that is detrimental to his health is this. It entails use of weapons, beatings, wounds, and other injuries. But from the perspective of domestic abuse, punishments like making a child stand in a corner or kneel on a pea, slapping and beating the back of the head, and making a child perform strenuous physical work are also acts of violence.

Although it is the most frequent kind of abuse, psychological abuse is also the most challenging to identify and address. Although the effects of psychological abuse might not manifest right away, they can result in significant mental disease. Psychological abuse takes many different forms. This can involve slander, humiliation, threats, coercion, extortion, minimizing successes, intimidation, and many forms of manipulation. Child neglect is a form of psychological child abuse. When parents ignore a child's difficulties, disregard his opinions, or ignore his demands, they are exhibiting themselves as parents. Psychological abuse can also have an indirect effect on other people. Typically, this involves threatening to harm someone else—parents, the wife, or pets. For example, a person is forced to do something, otherwise one of his relatives will suffer. Also, the manifestation of indirect psychological violence occurs when the child, for example, sees the violence of the father with the mother. In both cases, the violence itself is actually directed at another person, but it can cause psychological trauma no less than direct violence.

Sexual contact, sexual harassment, and coercion to engage in sexual activity all fall under the category of sexual violence. Typically, women and children are the ones who experience sexual abuse in the home. Most casualties among minors are young females. And if both men and women are capable of inflicting bodily and mental harm, then males are often those who commit sexual assault.

Economic violence in family life typically manifests as having a source of income, managing all family members' financial obligations, and refusing to provide the appropriate sum of money. Completely limiting a child's financial options is one way that violence towards children may emerge. So, for instance, if a husband forces his wife to quit her work, she is no longer able to support herself financially and becomes reliant on her spouse. This gives a guy complete authority over and control over his wife.

Various mental diseases can be the root of aggression against others. For instance, hallucinations or paranoid experiences in schizophrenia patients may lead to higher levels of violence. Affective bipolar disorder patients frequently experience psychomotor agitation, delusional ideas, and hallucinations during the manic phase. Additionally, this causes aggressive behavior to arise.

Alcohol, more precisely, the state of alcoholic intoxication, which is a person, is often the cause of physical and sexual violence. In this case, cognitive function decreases, critical perception, the desire to satisfy physiological needs comes to the fore, which is a common cause of sexual violence. That is why there are many children who are abused in alcoholic families.

The same situation occurs in people taking drugs or psychotropic substances. The existence of a family member who has experienced various forms of violence from childhood is another frequent cause of family violence. For instance, parents who experienced different forms of corporal punishment as children are more likely to discipline their children in the same way as an adult. In other words, violence is normalized in this household.

Also, the cause of domestic violence may be hidden in the individual characteristics of a person. For example, people with low self-esteem can prove themselves at the expense of the oppression of their loved ones, and people who lack self-confidence can do the same. Thus, the controlling type of people may try to subjugate everyone. Do not forget about the tendency to aggression. The more a person is prone to aggression, the more prone to violence.

When talking about the causes of domestic violence, it is necessary to mention the specific characteristics of the victims. There is a specific type of behavior called victimization. Criminologists define it as the illegal, immoral, or submissive behavior of the victim that causes the crime to be committed. Psychologists view victimization as a set of social, mental, and physical characteristics and personality traits that increase the likelihood of becoming a victim. Victims tend to provoke violence against themselves, and provocations can be both active and passive. Active provocations include all kinds of submissive behavior, and passive provocations include not resisting the abuser and unconditionally complying with all his demands. But despite the victimization of the victims, this does not remove the guilt and responsibility from the rapists.

Domestic abuse has serious repercussions that should never be taken lightly. Every year, three million kids see domestic abuse. As we previously indicated, data show that over 14,000 women and infants perish as a result of this every year. There are other injuries of various severity. The topic is bodily damage. But the psychological effects of domestic abuse are no less severe. And all animals are affected by this.

Despite the fact that males abuse women most often, there are instances of male abuse as well, particularly psychological abuse. There are three tiers of abuse's effects:

Injury (wounds, blows, burns, etc.), increased vulnerability to disease, and individual neglect on a bodily level. In terms of women, they run the chance of becoming pregnant unintentionally if compelled to have intercourse.

At the psychological level: post-traumatic stress, depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, suicide attempts, abuse of alcohol and other substances, sexual dysfunction, somatic diseases (headaches, gastrointestinal tract problems, general and non-specific anxiety, etc.), feelings of guilt, hopelessness and emptiness.

At the social level: mistrust and hostility towards everyone, social isolation, constant danger and a sense of threat from everything around.

The main focus of work to prevent domestic violence should be both general social and individual prevention, primarily involving the younger generation.

The complexity of the problem of domestic violence shows the need for a comprehensive strategy, the main goals of which are:

- prevention - public condemnation of family violence;
- protection - the application of law enforcement measures to ensure the safety of women in both public and private spheres of life; as well as holding persons who violate law and order accountable for their actions;
- provision - organization of state and non-state projects and organizations that provide professional support and consulting services.

It is crucial that comprehensive programs for the prevention of domestic abuse include the school and early childhood education systems as a key component. It is appropriate to talk about gender equality, the dynamics and painful effects of gender violence in any form, and to underline how these things are incompatible with human rights, love, respect, and a good family life in the context of educating young people about love and sexuality. Relationship conflicts are inevitable. However, there are situations when dispute resolution methods other than democratic discourse and productive discussions are applied. It is crucial to emphasize to boys and teenagers in sex education and non-violence education that a real man, a strong man, does not turn to physical violence even when he feels aggressive emotions, such as when he is verbally angry, jealous, or

when his girlfriend wants to break up with him. Girls and women are instructed not to put up with acts of violence, to never place responsibility on themselves, and to reject threats and brutal treatment. They should disclose the abuse to their friends, parents, or both, as opposed to keeping it a secret.

The list of measures aimed at preventing domestic violence includes:

- ✓ formation of social and cultural skills in family relations;
- ✓ explanation of mutual rights and obligations of family members;
- ✓ teaching methods of "peaceful" conflict resolution;

The most effective approach to preventing the recurrence of domestic violence is to treat both spouses, not just the victims, as this improves the quality of life for all family members. The form of family therapy is related to the teaching of social skills, which form the ways of socially adequate response in various situations in family members. In the process of such therapy, priority is usually given to behavioral methods, as a result of which the marital relationship improves, the emotional state of children and the motivation for recovery in families where the spouse is addicted to alcohol increase. Anti-alcohol treatment of women and men who abuse alcohol significantly reduces the risk of self-aggressive manifestations and improves family relationships.

As a result, it is important to take action at all levels to avoid domestic violence while also considering its causes. The set of measures prioritizes primary prevention, which calls for a shift in the population's conventional beliefs about the world. The system of medical and diagnostic support for victims of violent actions has to be improved, and general practitioners and the institution of family medicine need to be more widely accepted in light of the catastrophic repercussions of family violence. The effectiveness of preventative measures is also increased by the perpetrator and his victim receiving reciprocal counseling. The preventative strategy should be all-inclusive and provide victims of family violence with social, medical, psychological, psychotherapeutic, psychiatric, and legal support.

It should be noted that domestic violence won't cease until every child is raised in a loving home where the adults respect, cherish, and love one another. We serve as a role model for how to treat a wife or spouse. Make a fist or say something kind. Accept humiliation or provide a strong defense.

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